

ISic1425

Dedication to Enyo

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

30.09.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Naxos

Place of origin (modern)

Giardini-Naxos

Provenance

Area west of S. Venera (record on stone is 'Naxos 78, Scalia')

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 104387

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 26.5 cm

Width 19 cm

Depth 19 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. γύραρος

2. ἡῦρος

3. Ἐνῆσο[ι]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644975

PHI 195332

PHI 331342

Bibliography

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